

Change Management in Sri Lankan IT Projects

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Abstract:

Change management is critical to the success of IT projects, especially in dynamic and developing environments such as Sri Lanka. Despite the country's rapid technological progress, many IT projects face failure due to poor change strategies and limited research on proactive frameworks. This study investigates the strategic approaches companies use to manage change in IT project environments effectively. The research employed a qualitative methodology based on Kotter's 8-Step and ADKAR models. Data was collected through semi-structured interviews with senior project managers and a web-based survey among 41 IT professionals from two leading companies. Thematic analysis revealed communication, leadership, training, knowledge management, and risk assessment as key success factors. A model for proactive change management is proposed, emphasizing the integration of structured knowledge management into existing frameworks. The findings contribute to both theory and practice by extending change models and offering actionable insights for project managers in similar contexts.

Keywords: Change Management, Project Management, Information Technology, Kotter Model, ADKAR Model, Knowledge Management, Sri Lanka

1. Introduction

The rise of IT in Sri Lanka has brought about economic opportunities and modernization. However, poor change management remains a major cause of IT project failures. This study aims to identify and analyse the proactive strategies used by Sri Lankan IT companies to manage changes in project environments, thus bridging the theoretical and practical gaps in local project management practices.

2. Background

Change management in IT projects refers to the systematic process of planning, executing, and overseeing modifications to a project. Changes are a crucial factor when determining the success of a project, as they may significantly impact the project's scope, timeline, and budget. Efficiently implementing change management is vital for the success of every IT project. Organizations can increase the chances of successful project implementation by actively addressing significant variables that may limit change adoption. Therefore, based on the study aim mentioned above, the research question is: What are the company's proactive strategies considering the factors that affect the IT project's change management? This study systematically splits the main question into the objectives to achieve the research aim. Therefore, the general objective is to identify the company's proactive strategies, addressing the factors affecting IT project change management in Sri Lanka. Consequently, the sub-objectives are as follows.

- ❖ To recognize the influential factors that affect IT project's change management.
- ❖ To identify the company's feasible strategies addressing those factors.
- ❖ To clarify the project manager's role in change management.

Theoretically, the study considers ADKAR and Kotter's 8-step process models as fundamental change theories to reach the above research objectives. The ADKAR model is one of the wide-spread change management strategies that Jeff Haiyat has developed. It helps to understand and address the factors influencing successful change management adoption. In addition, John Kotter introduced eight steps of the change process that an organization could adopt when processing a project change. Empirically, this study considered a web survey questionnaire. The questionnaire was distributed to gather feedback from IT project managers and IT professionals in Sri Lanka. In addition, open-ended interviews were conducted with IT project managers in Sri Lanka for further clarification.

Scope of the study

Due to the lack of adequate studies on change management in IT project management. This study aims to identify the company's proactive strategies considering the factors affecting the accomplishment of the change management of the IT project. Therefore, the scope of this research is to identify the company's proactive strategies addressing the factors affecting the success of the change management process of the IT project in the Sri Lankan context. This study investigates the influence of the two management disciplines, change management and project management, on the success criteria of an information technology project. The target audience is IT organizations and IT professionals in Sri Lanka. The study collected data from forty-one IT professionals from two leading IT organizations in Sri Lanka as a target sample.

The place of study is Colombo, a city in Sri Lanka. The snowball and purposive sampling methods are used to select fifty participants. This survey ends when fifty questionnaires have been filled out or the ten-day time frame is over. Each participant is asked to complete a survey questionnaire to identify and evaluate any experience managing IT

project changes. Three project management professionals are also interviewed. Therefore, the study considers qualitative research and follows the inductive method in the entire investigation. The survey and open-ended interview tools used were Microsoft Forms and Microsoft Teams for the online interview. Therefore, the study's sample size is limited to fifty participants from both companies to gain more accurate results from experienced IT professionals in the software industry. The sample size is assumed to generate more reliable and accurate information for a larger population.

On the other hand, this research mainly focuses on human interaction. Therefore, the busy schedules of respondents can also be a barrier to collecting information. The data given by the sample would not be highly reliable as this study builds up considering personal attitudes. Finally, the researcher does not disclose the participants' and company names in this research. The study identified companies' proactive change management strategies in information technology project management, offering recommendations to project managers and other professionals to help them achieve goals in IT projects.

3. Theoretical Perspective

One of the most recent and popular prescriptions for planned organizational change is Kotter's Eight-Stage process of creating major change. Kotter has achieved 'guru-like' status and book club acclaim for his work in leading the understanding of organizational change and the heart of change. Essentially, Kotter proposes an eight-stage process, and once again, remnants of Lewin's original work are evident (Helms-Mills et al., 2009). John Kotter introduced the 8-Step Process for Leading Change to transform organizations. Kotter's Change is based on decades of empirical research and the latest thinking in brain science, organizational design, behavioral science, and business transformation. The process informs the most successful approaches to leading change and creating agile and adaptable organizations (Bedard, 2024).

However, there are varying viewpoints regarding its effectiveness, according to McLaren et al. (2023), the model's portrayal of the current condition has a harmful impact since it could cause anxiety and tension among employees. Sihite (2023) highlights that the fundamental reason for organizational change is because something relevant to the organization has changed or is about to change. Because of that, the organization had no choice but to change. This change occurred because of encouragement from internal and external companies. The decreased performance of its employees, which leads to unsatisfactory service, is often a trigger factor for internal organizations to make changes, and the external factor is increasingly fierce business competition. Furthermore, organizations must change in response to both internal and external influences. The model can be effectively utilized to facilitate this transformation. Morozov et al. (2018) analyze the application of Kotter's ideas in implementing systems in education and emphasize the beneficial influence on academic performance.

In addition, Lakdinu et al. (2022) stated that leadership, such as communication between employee's management, building central team output, top management dedication, and the quality of reengineering methods, navigate the execution of the victory in change management results and how those impact the success of ERP implementation. The model high-lights the significance of instilling a feeling of insistence, developing a vision and strategy, and empowering broad-based action, which can help organizations navigate through complex and uncertain situations. (McLaren et al., 2023).

While receiving criticisms and producing differing outcomes, Kotter's approach has been applied in various situations and can facilitate effective change initiatives. However, research conducted using Kotter's model in the information technology aspect is minimal. It is a top-down approach where the need for an approach to change originates at the top levels of the organization and then is promoted down through the organization's layers of management to the change recipients (Project Management Institute, 2021, p. 162).

Create urgency step Identify potential threats and opportunities that drive the need for change. Kotter highlighted the significance of developing a compelling rationale for change. Leaders must effectively convey the necessity for change in a manner that instills a compelling sense of urgency inside personnel. This entails the process of recognizing

potential risks and advantages, exchanging pertinent information, and demonstrating the possible outcomes of sustaining the current situation (Athuraliya, 2020; Project Management Institute, 2021, p. 162). Identifying the change leaders is a crucial step. Change leaders are not necessarily based on hierarchy. The change leaders should be influential people from various roles, with expertise, social and political importance. Achieving successful transformation needs robust leadership and support. A collective of influential individuals is established during this stage to lead the transformation process. The coalition should comprise individuals possessing a wide range of skills, experience, and influence inside the organization. Their primary responsibility is to advocate for change and assist in overcoming any opposition (Athuraliya, 2020; Project Management Institute, 2021, p. 162).

Figure 1. Kotter's Eight Step Model

The ADKAR model is a structured method for managing change, centering on an individual's development during organizational evolution. Jeff Hiatt created a framework consisting of five sequential components: awareness, motivation, understanding, proficiency, and reinforcement. These elements describe the typical stages of an individual's adaptation to a significant change (Project Management Institute, 2021, p.161). Hiatt and Creasey (2012) suggests the concept, which is comprised of two primary tiers. The first level pertains to the human aspect of transformation. The second level of analysis accounts for the many stages of a change project.

Research indicates that successful change management depends on the desire for individual acceptance and support. With that support, an organization can easily implement the desired change. Ali et al. (2021) suggest that leadership and human resource management practices are also crucial for inspiring employees to opt for and demonstrate a behavior change. The researcher has applied awareness and desire levels in the ADKAR model for the re-search. Found that leadership and human resource management practices are also impacted by individuals' initiation of changes from the change management perspective. She has applied awareness, ability, and reinforcement in the ADKAR model. In addition to successfully implementing change within an organization, several key areas must be addressed. These

include the ability to anticipate change, understand the impact of the scope of change, overcome resistance to change, develop a communication strategy to address resistance, possess cross-cultural skills, and secure top management's support for the organization's future vision. This has highlighted awareness ability and reinforcement in the ADKAR model (Hurn, 2012, pp. 41–46).

Abdallah and Mohammad (2016) argue that Prosci's ADKAR model is a commonly used objective-driven method that enables development management teams to concentrate on achieving outcomes, facilitating individual development. The model operates under the assumption that organizations themselves remain static, but the individuals inside organizations are the ones who change. ADKAR defines effective change at the personal level and delineates the objectives or results of successful change. The tool is beneficial for designing Change Management activities, identifying deficiencies, formulating remedial measures, and assisting managers and team leaders.

Therefore, the emphasized research is focused on organizational change management. Further research is required to examine how the ADKAR model effectively and proactively manages IT project changes. ADKAR model consists of five steps: Awareness, desire, knowledge, ability, and reinforcement. The awareness step focuses on why the change is necessary. During the Awareness stage, individuals must comprehend the rationale for the change and its implications for themselves and the company. It entails developing a comprehension of the imperative nature of change and the underlying rationales behind it. Effective communication is essential to efficiently distribute information regarding the change (Hiatt & Creasey, 2012, p. 47). In addition, In the desired step, people know why the change is necessary; there needs to be a desire to be part of and support the change. Desire entails cultivating an individual's dedication to the transformation. Individuals must possess intrinsic motivation to endorse and engage in the transformation process. The process entails acknowledging and resolving issues, cultivating a favorable mindset, and showcasing the advantages of the change on both the organizational and individual fronts (Hiatt & Creasey, 2012, p.47).

According to the knowledge step, people must understand how to change, including new processes and systems and roles and responsibilities. Knowledge can be imparted through training and education. Knowledge provides individuals with the necessary information and abilities to comprehend and effectively implement change. This phase involves providing instruction and dissemination of information to guarantee that individuals possess the requisite expertise to adjust to the novel procedures or systems (Hiatt & Creasey, 2012, p. 48).

In the ability step, knowledge is supported by hands-on practice, access to expertise, and help as needed. Ability is the phase in which individuals effectively convert knowledge into practical action. They must possess the necessary abilities and competence to execute the transformation effectively. During this phase, it is crucial to provide individuals with practical training, hands-on experience, and continuing support to ensure their confidence and competence in implementing the new methods of working (Hiatt & Creasey, 2012, p. 48). Finally, Reinforcement supports the sustainment of the change. This can include rewards, recognition, feedback, and measurement. Reinforcement entails maintaining the alteration and guaranteeing its enduring achievement.

Figure 2. ADKAR Model

4. Research design and methodology

The research design refers to the plan or strategy that outlines how the research can be conducted. Key research designs are quantitative research design, qualitative research design, mixed methods research design, experimental research design, and observation research de-sign. Among those, this research has adopted a qualitative research design since it tried to understand the IT professionals' thoughts, feelings, opinions, and reasons behind these successfully executed changes in IT projects.

The study area is the location or the place where the research is directed. This study was conducted in the capital city of Colombo, Sri Lanka, where most IT tech companies operate. This study obtained its information from the two leading IT companies. As this research aims to find out companies' proactive strategies of the selected respondents, the researcher mainly used qualitative methods; according to the author's perspective, this research follows not only a case study strategy but also an action research strategy because case study strategy is an in-depth study of a specific individual or phenomenon in its existing context. In contrast, action research focuses on solving an immediate problem or working with others to solve problems and address issues.

However, both survey questionnaires and open-ended interview methods were used, considering that all human beings are difficult to understand to study their attitudes. Various techniques and tools can be used. It also needs more than one approach. Hence, qualitative methods have been used to gather more reliable data as the researcher wants to analyze the findings statistically. Qualitative research involves gathering and analyzing qualitative data through open-ended communication. Its primary aim is to comprehend individuals' thoughts, opinions, emotions, and the underlying reasons behind these feelings (Cornell, 2022). A survey is an investigation of the characteristics of a given population by collecting data from a sample of that population and estimating their characteristics through the systematic use of statistical methodology. In addition, when studying complex social phenomena involving human experiences, attitudes, and behaviors, qualitative methods can capture the richness and distinctions of these aspects. It provides a more holistic view of the subject matter (Lazar et al., 2017).

Figure 3. Research Methodology

4.1 Sampling method

The study selected the two leading IT companies as a sample from Colombo City, Sri Lanka, where most software companies conduct their business operations. Snowball and purposive sampling were used to develop the research sample. According to these methods, a sample was selected covering all three research objectives. For that, the researcher selected fifty IT professionals from two leading IT organizations, respectively. They are under different age categories, experiences, and job designations. From that fifty samples, three senior project experts from both organizations be interviewed to identify exact opinions regarding change management in IT projects. According to Wilson (2014) Interviews are a standard tool for data collection among business and management students. Interviews are more commonly associated with a qualitative research strategy. Interviewing allows the researcher to gain insight into a person's beliefs and attitudes towards a particular subject. A vital advantage of some types of interviews is that it allows one to examine verbal and non-verbal communication.

5. Empirical findings

The researcher conducted open-ended interviews and a survey questionnaire as a tool to fulfill the data-gathering requirements. The survey questionnaire was semi-structured using a five-point Likert scale. The interviews and survey questionnaires aimed to identify the company's proactive strategies addressing the factors affecting the accomplishment of the change management of the IT project in the Sri Lankan context. The survey questionnaire was made easy for respondents by adding five-point Likert scale methods for some questions. Because most respondents dislike and are reluctant to write answers to the questions since they must invest more time in them.

Open-ended interviews have been conducted to gain more insight into participants' experiences. Interview questions are similar to survey questionnaires. The interview questionnaire can be found in Appendix 3. Following the main objective, the three sub-objectives, including recognizing the influential factors of change management, identifying the company's possible strategies considering those factors, and understanding the role of a project manager in perceiving the influence of change management in Sri Lankan IT projects. The survey questionnaire was sent to the professionals, and the study got responses from forty-one IT professionals within ten days. Also, the researcher conducted three interviews with senior IT project managers at companies A and Z among forty-one respondents.

6. Discussion of findings

The study found various prioritized factors related to change management, such as proper communication, top management, and training support. These influential factors interact with each other in complex ways and can vary depending on the specific context of the IT project. By carefully considering and addressing these factors, project managers can increase the likelihood of successful change management and achieve desired project outcomes. Following demonstrate identified key factors from survey questionnaire and interviews.

6.1 Interpretation of the Influential Factors Affecting IT Project's Change Management

6.1.1 Proper communication

The results indicate factors such as the importance of clear communication about the purpose and benefits of the change. Communication is essential for keeping all stakeholders informed, engaged, and motivated along the change pathways. Communicate timely and transparent messages, especially concerns, to build community and solicit input to help address change resistance. Also, the Project Management Institute (2021) highlighted how proper communication helps keep stakeholders updated regarding project status. Solid Communication helps provide sufficient information regarding project timelines and expectations. This factor is also related to user feedback communication and concerns with related changes in ongoing IT projects.

This covers official communication of project-related information while engaging stakeholders effectively. This is an accepted form of unofficial communication which happens inside the project. Some keywords or phrases that emerged in this theme were clear communication, sufficient information, efficient communication channels for user feedback, and concern. Based on interviews conducted by the author, Participant One and Participant Three also highlighted the importance of proper communication when executing an IT project. They mentioned that effective communication ensures that all stakeholders, including team members, clients, and management, clearly understand project goals, requirements, timelines, and deliverables. This alignment prevents misunderstandings and helps keep everyone on the same page throughout the project lifecycle. Furthermore, effective communication builds collaboration among team members, facilitating knowledge sharing, brainstorming, and problem-solving, which are essential for project success. In addition, in the survey questionnaire, out of forty-one participants, 97.6% selected clear communication about the

purpose, which means effective communication plays a significant portion in executing successful change in IT projects in Sri Lanka. The responses received for this question are listed in the appendices

6.1.2 Top management support

As top management support is considered one of the critical success factors in project management, effective executive involvement can significantly improve project success. Leadership is outside of the authority and position power of the project manager and project team. Active engagement and oversight by a project sponsor support the project manager and team and ultimately drive project outcomes.

This includes providing necessary resource allocation, decision-making authority, and guidance in managing risk, and this does not cover technical expertise, detailed technical decisions, and daily project management. In this theme, some keywords or phrases that emerged were right leadership, resistant management, Top management support, and company culture, which also reflects some aspects. On the other hand, during the interview, Participant One highlighted that leaders are providing strategic guidance, leveraging their influence to address external challenges, and gathering support from higher levels of the organization if needed. In addition, 80.5% of participants selected leadership support in managing resistance in the survey questionnaire provided, which means top management plays a significant role in executing successful change in IT projects in Sri Lanka.

6.1.3 Training

When executing changes in IT projects in Sri Lanka, providing training and support is crucial to ensure the successful adoption of new technologies, processes, or systems. This includes providing necessary training, such as sharing user manuals, on-site support and coaching, and workshops. During interviews, some keywords or phrases emerged in this theme: Training, Adequate user training, and support for the new IT system. Furthermore, Participant Two and Participant Three highlighted that training programs provide team members with the necessary skills and knowledge to utilize these new resources effectively.

By investing in training, organizations ensure that their workforce is equipped to handle the changes and maximize the benefits they bring. In addition, survey questionnaire outcomes demonstrate that training supports a significant portion of executing successful change in IT projects in Sri Lanka.

6.2 Explanation of the Company's Feasible Strategies Addressing the Factors.

To address the influential factors of change management affecting IT projects, companies can implement a range of feasible strategies tailored to their specific context and needs. Following are the key factors highlighted during the interviews and survey questionnaire.

6.2.1 Knowledge Management System (KMS)

Knowledge management systematically manages an organization's knowledge assets to create value and meet tactical and strategic requirements. It consists of the processes, strategies, and systems that sustain and enhance knowledge creation, storage, and sharing. This includes all systems to manage and open up an organization's information (Uit Beijerse, 2000). Knowledge management systems may provide access to training materials, documentation, and resources related to IT projects, but they may not offer comprehensive training and development functionalities specific to change management.

During the interviews, Participant One and Participant Two highlighted how knowledge management systems help execute changes in an IT project. Some keywords or phrases in this theme were knowledge, knowledge management system implementation, change management system, sufficient information, and lessons learned. Furthermore, they

emphasized that the knowledge management system plays a vital role in executing changes within IT projects by providing a platform for knowledge sharing, learning, collaboration, decision support, and continuous improvement. By utilizing the capabilities of a KMS, organizations can enhance their change management processes.

6.2.2 Risk Assessment

Survey questionnaire participants highlighted that risk assessment is also helpful in successfully driving change in an IT project. A risk is an uncertain event or condition that, if it occurs, can have a positive or negative effect on one or more objectives. Identified risks may or may not materialize in a project. Project teams endeavor to identify and evaluate known and emergent risks, both internal and external to the project, throughout the life cycle.

However, risk assessment does not include business continuity, Legal/compliance risk, or human factors. Some keywords or phrases in this theme were risk assessment and risk management. The examples and themes are extracted from the survey questionnaire shared with the participants. In their twenty-seven times, participants selected risk assessment options.

6.2.3 Identification of the Necessary Changes

Thomas (2023) states that the Change Management Process is used to initiate, record, assess, approve, and resolve project changes. Project changes are needed when the scope, time, or cost of one or more previously approved project deliverables changes. Most changes affect the budget and project schedule.

During the interview, participants also highlighted that by identifying the needed changes, project stakeholders can align their efforts toward common objectives, ensuring that the project stays focused and targeted. Project teams can accurately estimate resource requirements and allocate resources effectively to ensure the successful execution of the project. According to the survey questionnaire, a response theme has been extracted. This element focuses on building the rationale to help people understand why change is needed and how the future state will be better with that change. This covers identifying the need for the change and obtaining approval from the obligated stakeholders to execute the changes.

6.3 Interpretation of the Project Manager's Role in Change Management.

The results indicate that most respondents decided that project managers play a crucial role in planning, executing, and adapting the change management process. The role of a project manager in an IT project is multifaceted and crucial for success. Project managers in IT projects are responsible for forming business and stakeholder alignment, utilizing various influence tactics. They must possess diverse skills and tools to ensure project success in the technology sector. Additionally, project managers play a significant role in an IT project by utilizing project management methodologies.

The project management process is essential for coordinating decisions, planning, and personnel in IT projects, impacting enterprises' efficiency and strategic development. This includes how the project manager's role is vital to execute changes inside the IT project. A project manager is generally considered to be the person responsible for delivering a project on time, within budget, and according to the quality standards specified by the client (Somerville et al., 2010). Various sources of literature discuss the roles and functions a project manager executes.

Somerville and Campbell (2001) differentiate between three roles/function skill areas: communication, mentoring, and technical. Griffith and Watson (2004) describe the functions of a project manager as forecasting, planning, organizing, controlling, motivating, coordinating, and communicating.

Three interview participants highlighted that project managers play a vital role in executing changes in IT projects by providing leadership, planning and coordination, stakeholder management, risk management, resource allocation, quality assurance, and communication and reporting. Project managers execute successful change implementation by effectively fulfilling these responsibilities and ensuring project objectives are achieved on time and within budget.

Similarly, from survey questions, 75% of participants indicated that project managers play a crucial role in planning, executing, and adapting the change management process (see Appendix 8).

According to the analysis conducted based on three research questions, the researcher has found that proper communication, receiving leadership support to execute changes, and training support are influential factors of change management that affect IT project success in Sri Lanka. On the other hand, maintaining sound knowledge management systems, conducting risk assessments, and identifying the precise requirements of changes are the company's possible strategies considering the factors in Sri Lanka. Finally, project managers play a crucial role in change management in IT projects by managing cost, quality, and Time.

7. Conclusion

The study identifies the company's proactive strategies considering the factors affecting the success of the change management of the IT project. Researchers investigate this requirement by setting up three sub-objectives. The researcher has come across proper communication, leadership support to execute changes, and training support as influential factors of change management that affect IT project success in the Sri Lankan context. On the other hand, maintaining sound knowledge management systems, conducting risk assessments, and identifying the precise requirements of particular changes are identifying the company's possible strategies for addressing the factors in Sri Lanka.

Finally, project managers play a crucial role in change management in IT projects by managing cost, quality, and time. With this research, the researcher was able to fulfill the lack of sufficient previous research studies on this topic as most of the researchers are targeted on change management of organizations but not the change management in IT project management. Neither of those studies indicated what proactive strategies the company needs to take to manage influential factors affecting the success of change management in the IT project. Therefore, the expected research aim has been achieved. With this study, the company will be able to develop a model for a proactive change management approach, which can help to manage the requirement of changes and reduce the risk of project failure. Additionally, implementing a proactive change management solution with effective procedures for managing project changes can ensure successful project completion and higher-quality outcomes.

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